

Emotional branding by mascot

Role of mascot branding an Indian case study

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Abstract:

In this paper the role of mascot in emotional branding is described with an Indian case study. This paper examines the effectiveness of Mascot branding with various theories of emotional design. A study of mascot branding strategies of few national, multinational companies has been done. The paper investigates to what extent the mascot campaign has caught the people's attention, emotions of people for mascot and understanding of mascot from people's perception. Various emotional responses associated with mascots are studied. This can help designers and corporate to add an emotional brand value by effective design and use of mascot.

Key words: Emotional Branding, Mascot.

1. Introduction

Mascots have been widely used for corporate identity and to get public attention. Local and global businesses use mascots for products and services. This paper examines the effectiveness of mascot branding supported with a Indian case study. Due to increasing use of mascot, effective design procedure is a need of time. The mascot has been widely used as a symbol for visual identity all over the world in all business domains. Designers must know the primary factors for mascot design from user perspective. This case study initiates a direction for designers to make their efforts on designing a good mascot as a corporate identity.

2. Method

The objective of this paper is to examine the effectiveness of mascot branding, especially in India by reviewing insights discussed, the literature and by investigating the understanding of the public about a mascot. It analyzes to what extent mascot branding has caught the public attention, affection and goes on to identify the lessons one can learn for the improvement of organization branding. The methodology adopted by this research is, by nature, essentially interpretative, based on theoretical insights, with case studies, which can enrich existing theories. Our evaluation of branding is based mainly on a review of the literature and study of relevant documents, interviews and statistical approach. Questionnaires were randomly distributed at locations to represent various strata of society. The respondents were asked to write down few adjectives for mascots, there were also open-ended questions so that, respondents were able to provide additional views and make suggestions in free-text form. In total, 30 people participated in the survey. Among them, 30% of respondents were campus residents, 30% were semiliterate, and 40% were from middle class families. All the subjects were in normal mental state. Subjects were asked to write various positive attributes (adjectives) about mascots. Six mascots were international, having presence in India. Two mascots were having Indian background. This mascot characters are from different business fields like Olympic Games, a Soft Drink Corporate, Industrial Paint Manufacturer, and a Dairy Product Industry as shown in *Figure 1*. Stories associated with mascot creation, use, market impact made etc. are collected and analyzed.

3. Branding

A company needs to adopt the right strategies in order to brand itself successfully. Successful branding depends greatly on the identification of distinctive and defining characteristics possessed by the organization and people's perception, experience of the brand. The brand of a product embodies a set of physical and socio-psychological attributes as well as beliefs that are associated with the product (Simoes and Dibb, 2001)¹. Branding is a deliberate strategy to select some attributes of a product as core values in order to facilitate the process by which consumers confidently recognize and appreciate those attributes (De Chernatony and Dall'Olmo Riley, 1998)². Product's identity can be formed from those core values. Brands are acting as ambassadors to represent the company. People often translate their perceptions (imagery, feelings, evaluations, and judgments) into their own understandable identity of the brands. A strong business identity is an essential marketing tool in the global business environment for a company, products, services it sells. Businesses must develop their corporate identities by various means. It is important that a brand have a uniform image globally. Brand should generate revenues. It should last long for business survival and victory.

3.1 Emotions and mascot

Mascots have been widely used as symbols for visual identity in contests such as the Olympic Games, arousing public attention. Mascot creates emotional bonding, and establishing corporate identity. By paralleling mascot design with communication process, the mascot can be equated with sign vehicles in the symbolic environment. To be visually effective, the vehicles must be properly designed. Mascot plays an increasingly prominent role in corporate identity. Through subsequent objective interpretation, designers can grasp the main factors in cognition of mascot design. With knowledge of the symbolic interaction between users and mascots, designers can demonstrate more creativity in their products. A Study of cognitive human factors in mascot design³ can help to achieve effective mascot design. Emotional needs and affective needs are terms with a design origin. These are basically the needs of users of products, services, systems and so forth, satisfaction of which may evoke affective responses. McDonagh and Lebbon (2000)⁴ refer to the needs related to soft functionality issues, i.e. those needs beyond the basic functionality and utility issues, such as sentimentality, aesthetics, personal taste, touch, smell, feel and personality. Product attachment is a core issue in the field of design and emotion. Lately attachment itself is considered as a design strategy within a sustainable research agenda. For example, Mugge et al. (2008)⁵ set particular design strategies forth in order to create product attachment. Personalization is proposed as a strategy to build a meaningful relationship between users and their products. In the first conference on Design and Emotion in 1999, a aim was to support designers with tools and methods to create a valuable product-user relationship (Overbeeke and Hekkert, 1999)⁶. This type of relationship with brand can be established by means of mascot. Chapman (2005)⁷ states the significance of creating a narrative between the product and the user, in which the user can generate new meanings through the relationship, to keep the relationship alive. In all these studies there is a tendency to create an emotionally evocative bond between the user and the product. This type of narrative relationship with mascot is observed by the author in this study. Norman (2004)⁸ also focuses on affect and the levels of affective processing in his book on emotional design. According to his framework, affect may arise due to three levels differing in cognitive involvement: visceral, behavioral and reflective levels. In the visceral level, mostly automatic and universal affective responses are produced, such as pleasure in response to smooth curves or smiling faces. The behavioral level is responsible for affect generated by everyday behavior, such as satisfactory completion of a task. The reflective level is the most sophisticated level and controls the pleasure due to intellectual processes, such as the pleasure in decoding the hidden meanings of a poem. Norman (2004) translates these different levels to different strategies for emotional design. Visceral design focuses on the automatic responses to the appearance of a product, behavioral design essentially deals with the ease and efficiency of use, and reflective design primarily focuses on the personal and cultural meanings of products.

3.2. Observations

Mascots provided various emotional responses as shown in *Table 1*. Author analyzed that looking at a smiling face of a mascot subject's response satisfies a visceral level. Mascot's different postures give behavioral satisfaction of daily routine activities. In reflective level, curiosity is aroused and peoples try to give personal, cultural meaning to the mascots. Our study observed type of narrative bonding with mascot and hence products. Many respondents easily identified the brands and products associated with each mascot. Mascot narrates a story and establishes a relation between products, services as discussed earlier. Some mascot branding used real time, contextual stories happening around the world as shown in *Figure 2* which is appreciated by public and creates more emotional responses like bonding, satire, smile, pleasure, anger etc. It generates curiosity at various levels. Mascot makes brand alive, distinct and becomes a familiar member for a community. People like cute, chubby baby faces but they accept properly designed oblong facial proportions, thin body parts. This can be observed in *Figure1-B1, B2*. Some observant build own stories around the mascot during study.

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Figure: 1 Mascots used for this study

Table1. Verbal Analysis

Mascot Group	Figure number	Adjectives used by people (Few responses from the respondents)	Brand objective	Agreement in percentage
Group 1	A1 A2 A3 A4 A5	Birdlike, Sky, Curious, Welcoming Tree Like, Leaves ,Smiling Fire, Warm, Curious Sun, Motion, Dynamic, Smiling, Sporty Green, Earth, Bird, Sustainable, Smiling	Somewhat Similar	67 %
Group 2	B1 B2	Playful, stylish, Liberal, Crazy, skill Relax, sleeping, cool, Informal, Thin	Similar	80 %
Group 3	C1	Kid, chubby, cute, Mischievous Girl	Similar	76 %
Group 4	D1 D2	Teenager, Middle Class Boy, Curious Artist, Mischievous, A Painter Child	Similar	73 %

Brand specific comments not considered here.

4. Case study from India

Amul (Anand Milk-Producers Union Ltd.)

The Brand Amul is a movement in dairy cooperative in India. It is leading dairy brand of Asia. For forty years continuously, company relied only on a single theme behind its advertisements. The mascot based theme that is talked about more than three generations. A theme that has one of the high brand recalls. Mascot based branding efforts has been internationally appreciated for its consistency, wits. Amul sales figures have jumped from 1000 tonnes a year in 1966 to over 25,000 tonnes a year in 1997. No other brand comes even close to it. All because a thumb-sized girl climbed on to the hoardings and put a spell on the masses. It is a four-year-old, in unable to curb her curiosity who draws her attention to the hoarding that has come up overnight. She was a favorite topic of discussion for the next one week and people loved it. Everywhere somehow or the other the campaign always seemed to crop up in conversation. Friday star, round eyed, chubby cheeked, winking at you, are the few adjectives for this mascot. Hoardings are strategically placed at many traffic lights. People stop, look, chuckled at the hoarding that casts her dressed in her little polka dotted dress and a red and white bow, holding out her favorite pack. Amul girl is playing the role of a social observer. Over the years, the campaign acquired that important touch. These evocative humour advertisements are not just a source of amusement. They make aware of what is happening around. Many believe that the charm lies in the catchy lines. Company website is having different contextual stories named topical, greetings, animations based on this mascot. Recent sales turnover of company is 67113 million Indian rupees⁹. Public, and especially the children, like things that are cute and little. It is something appealing. When people laugh at, it is because she is so human; and that is the secret of her popularity. Thus, mascot can play an important role in brand development of an organization.

Fig.2.A mascot with contextual stories

Fig.3.An Inter relationship

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6. Conclusions

Mascots are closer to living form so, they are emotionally affiliated to human beings. The relationship between emotions, branding, and mascot can be made clear from Figure 3. Mascots, characters have a story associated with them like that of a person or a customer. Mascots are able to show emotions unlike other trademarks Thus mascots have more chances of emotional acceptance and set bonding between customer and product or services. Generally, a textual or abstract logo is used as a trademark, which is emotionally less appealing and needs good cognition level. There can be various uses of mascot like it serves as a brand ambassadors, which never retires. Mascots can help to generate revenue by various formats such as merchandising and gaming in addition to core business. Mascot should be designed to adhere to a brand's image and it can have different emotional reaction. Design elements such as line, color, and graphics should be carefully used for mascot effectiveness. Consumer's perception regarding mascot may vary to some extent but core emotions remain the same. Mascots have good entertainment value. Mascots can be intelligently and flexibly used for branding. Mascots and trademarks alone cannot be a deciding factor for a successful business but they can help in Emotional branding of product and services.

7. References

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- ¹⁰ Image courtesy to respective brand owners.